

On the Electrolytic Behaviour of Triorganoarsenic(v) Aryloxides

K. C. MALHOTRA, NEERAJ SHARMA* and S. C. CHAUDHRY

Department of Chemistry, Himachal Pradesh University, Summer Hill, Shimla-171 005

Manuscript received 2 December 1991, accepted 4 June 1992

Triphenylarsenic dichlorides and their hydrolysed products such as $\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OH})\text{X}$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OH})_2$ have been investigated conductometrically¹. Triphenylarsine dihydroxide $\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OH})_2$ is a non-electrolyte and does not contain five-coordinate arsenic and exists as $\text{Ph}_3\text{AsO} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}^2$ while compounds Ph_3AsCl_2 and $\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OH})\text{X}$ are five-coordinate and reported to be weak electrolytes^{3,4}. Triphenylhydroxy halides are known to form stable compounds of composition $(\text{Ph}_3\text{AsOH}^+)_2\text{HgCl}_4$, $\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OH})^+\text{ClO}_4^-$ with mercuric chloride and silver perchlorate⁴. We have reported⁵ the synthesis of triorganoarsenic(v) aryloxide of composition $\text{Ph}_3\text{AsCl}_{2-n}(\text{OAr})_n$, where $n=1$ or 2. These com-

pounds are quite stable and behave as weak electrolytes. In view of the interesting behaviour of $\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OH})\text{Cl}$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OH})_2$ in non-aqueous solvents mentioned above, it is considered worthwhile to explore the electrolytic behaviour of triorganoaryloxides of arsenic(v) in the presence of strong chloride ion acceptors and alkali metal aryloxides.

Results and Discussion

The compounds $\text{Ph}_3\text{AsCl}(\text{OAr})$ are fairly stable compounds having melting points in the range 105–160°. They are soluble in nitrobenzene and conductance does not change with time. Conductometric

titrations therefore between $\text{Ph}_3\text{AsCl(OAr)}$ and various chloride ion acceptors such as SbCl_5 , AlCl_3 , FeCl_3 etc., have been carried out in this solvent at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The solutions of parent aryloxy $\text{Ph}_3\text{AsCl(OAr)}$ have significant conductance but with the addition of a very dilute solutions of chloride ion acceptors in the same solvent, a continuous decrease in conductance has been observed. This observation, as a matter of fact is in contrast to the previous observation made on monochloro phenoxy and naphthoxy derivatives of titanium(IV), niobium(V) and tantalum(V)⁶ wherein an increase in conductance was observed on the addition of chloride ion acceptors. It is evident from the conductance composition curves (Fig. 1) that there

Fig. 1. Conductance composition curves: (Δ) $\text{Ph}_3\text{AsCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)$ vs SbCl_5 , (\bullet) $\text{Ph}_3\text{AsCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl})$ vs AlCl_3 , (\circ) $\text{Ph}_3\text{AsCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3)$ vs AlCl_3 and (\square) $\text{Ph}_3\text{AsCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3)$ vs FeCl_3 .

are sharp breaks at 1 : 1 molar ratio suggesting the possibility of formation of compounds of 1 : 1 stoichiometry. Very low conductance of the solution at the end of the titration suggests that the compounds of the type $\text{Ph}_3\text{As(OAr)SbCl}_6$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{As(OAr)M}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_4$ are predominantly covalent in character and perhaps exist as undissociated ion-pairs. These curves may be rationalised in terms of the following reactions,

These compounds as evidenced from the conductance studies have been actually isolated as solid compounds in separate experiments and are listed in Table 1. Molar conductance values of millimolar solutions of these compounds were too low to be

assigned to ionic solids. In the ir spectra of these compounds, sharp and new bands at 622 and 335 cm^{-1} , 492 and 400 cm^{-1} (not present in parent compound) have been assigned to $(\text{Sb}-\text{Cl})^7$, $(\text{Al}-\text{Cl})^8$ and $(\text{Fe}-\text{Cl})^9$ modes in SbCl_6^- , AlCl_4^- and FeCl_4^- respectively. The formation of polymeric anions such as Al_2Cl_7^- is excluded because there is no band at 300–315 cm^{-1} (Ref. 10).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF THE TRIORGANOMONOCHLOROARSENIC(V) ARYLOXIDES WITH LEWIS ACIDS

Compd.	Analysis% Found/ (Cald.)		Mol. cond.* $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
	As	Cl	
$\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)\text{SbCl}_6$	9.54 (9.61)	18.18 (18.23)	3.4
$\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3)\text{AlCl}_4$	11.92 (12.02)	22.67 (22.76)	2.2
$\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3)\text{FeCl}_4$	11.98 (11.95)	22.45 (22.66)	1.1
$\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl})\text{AlCl}_4$	12.14 (12.44)	28.96 (29.48)	1.8

*In PhNO_2

Conductometric titration plots of $\text{Ph}_3\text{As(OAr)}_2$ versus alkali metal aryloxides carried out in nitrobenzene also show similar trends of conductance composition curves and have sharp breaks at 1 : 1 molar ratio. Unlike the contrasting behaviour of $\text{Ph}_3\text{As(OH)}_2$ compared to $\text{Ph}_3\text{As(OH)Cl}$, it is observed that $\text{Ph}_3\text{As(OAr)}_2$ behaves identically as $\text{Ph}_3\text{As(OAr)Cl}$, both contain five-coordinate arsenic. Conductance composition curves are shown in Fig. 2. A trend of decrease in conductance of solutions on addition of alkali metal aryloxides

Fig. 2. Conductance composition curves: (Δ) $\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2$ vs $\text{KOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2$, (\square) $\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3)_2$ vs $\text{NaOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3$, (\bullet) $\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_2$ vs $\text{NaOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}$ and (\circ) $\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3)_2$ vs $\text{LiOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3$.

with a sharp break at 1:1 molar ratio may be explained as

wherein the formation of undissociated ion-pair $\text{M}^+[\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OAr})_3]^-$ has been postulated. These double aryloxides, as indicated by conductance composition curves, have also been actually isolated in separate experiments by reacting the components in equimolar ratio under reflux. The stoichiometric composition of these compounds has been established by elemental analysis (Table 2). Molar conductance values of millimolar solution of these compounds suggest that they are predominantly non-ionic in character and exist as ion-pairs.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF DOUBLE ARYLOXIDES OF TRIORGANOARSENIC(V) ARYLOXIDES

Compd.	Analysis % (Calcd.)		Mol. cond.* $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
	As	Alkali metal	
$\text{Li}[\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3)_2]$	9.58 (9.85)	0.86 (0.92)	1.05
$\text{K}[\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2]$	9.79 (9.86)	5.08 (5.13)	2.13
$\text{Na}[\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3)_2]$	10.28 (10.73)	3.12 (3.29)	1.87
$\text{Na}[\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_2]$	10.12	3.0	1.65
In PhNO_2	(10.52)	(3.23)	

Unlike the contrasting behaviour reported earlier in literature¹¹ in case of $\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OH})\text{Cl}$ and $\text{Ph}_2\text{As}(\text{OH})_2$, it has been observed that the triorganoarsenic(v) aryloxides of composition $\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OAr})\text{Cl}$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OAr})_2$ both contain five coordinated arsenic and are weak electrolytes.

Experimental

Compounds of composition $\text{Ph}_3\text{AsCl}(\text{OAr})$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{As}(\text{OAr})_2$ were prepared⁵ by reacting Ph_3AsCl_3 with the corresponding phenols in appropriate molar ratio in the presence of Et_3N . Alkali metal aryloxides were prepared by reacting phenols with alkali metals in benzene. Conductance measurements were made in a specially designed Y-shaped cell-jacket fitted with a cell (cell constant 0.328). All operations were made under perfectly anhydrous conditions.

References

1. A. E. GODDARD, "A Text Book of Inorganic Chemistry", ed. J. N. FRIEND, Griffin & Co. Ltd London, 1930, Vol. XI, Part 2, pp. 123, 130.
2. D. M. L. GOODGAME and F. A. COTTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2298.
3. A. D. BEVERIDGE and G. S. HARRIS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 6076; A. D. BEVERIDGE, G. S. HARRIS and F. INGLIS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1966, 520.
4. B. J. HATHAWAY and A. E. UNDERHILL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3091; A. E. WICKENDEN and R. A. KRAUSE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 404.
5. N. SHARMA, B. S. GOLEN, R. K. MAHAJAN and S. C. CHAUDHRY, *Polyhedron*, 1991, 10, 789.
6. K. C. MALHOTRA, U. K. BANERJEE, K. C. MAHAJAN and S. C. CHAUDHRY, *Curr. Sci.*, 1982, 51, 1018; K. C. MALHOTRA, K. MAHAJAN and S. C. CHAUDHRY, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1983, 8, 348; K. C. MALHOTRA, U. K. BANERJEE and S. C. CHAUDHRY, *Curr. Sci.*, 1979, 48, 816.
7. D. COOK, S. J. KUHN and G. A. OLAH, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1960, 33, 1669.
8. R. J. H. CLARK, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, 21, 955.
9. C. DJORDJEVIC, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, 21, 301; D. M. ADAMS, J. CHATT, J. M. DAVIDSON and J. GERRATT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2189.
10. E. RYTTER, H. A. OYE, S. J. CYVIN and B. N. CYVIN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, 55, 1185.
11. G. S. HARRIS and F. INGLIS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 497.